

What happens when VGI is threatened? An analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OpenStreetMap

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† The views expressed are purely those of the author and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

This abstract was accepted to the OSMScience 2024 Conference after peer-review.

OpenStreetMap (OSM) operates on optimistic principles: it assumes that a diverse crowd can collaboratively agree on project goals and the methods to achieve them. This presumption of goodwill among participants is, for the most part, validated by OSM's success. However, there are instances where these assumptions are challenged, such as disagreements over tag usage [1], the mapping of general feature types [2], or specific entities [3]. When unresolved, these disputes can escalate into "editing wars," where users engage in repeated edits to enforce their views [4]. Despite such conflicts, the involved parties generally do not contest OSM's overarching objective of producing an accurate global map. Deviations from this goal, classified as platform abuse [5], include actions like spamming (e.g., using OSM for promotional purposes) and vandalism, where edits intentionally misrepresent on-the-ground reality. These abuses, particularly vandalism, pose significant risks to the project's success, as an inaccurate map can render OSM unusable in many contexts. Such incidents are not uncommon, as evidenced by an analysis of user bans [6]. Academic studies on this issue have primarily focused on detecting vandalism, e.g. [7], and analyzing specific cases' impacts on data integrity, e.g. [8]. OSM's primary responses to vandalism include post-hoc data reverts, which any user can perform, and user bans issued by the Data Working Group (DWG), the OSM Foundation body responsible for handling data-related issues such as copyright infringement and abuse [9]. Recently, OSM introduced a daily rate limit in response to a particularly severe vandalism case, marking a shift towards proactive vulnerability mitigation [10]. This paper documents and analyzes the events that led to the implementation of the rate limit, aiming to understand better through these events the factors influencing OSM's resilience and vulnerability.

The chain of events began on October 20, 2023, when members of the OSM_Israel Telegram group [11] reported an instance of vandalism. By the following evening, it became apparent that this was part of a coordinated effort involving newly created accounts

Grinberger, A. Y., & Minghini, M. (2025). What happens when VGI is threatened? An analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OpenStreetMap.

In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.). Proceedings of OSM Science 2024, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024.

Available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2024>. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17369467](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17369467)

systematically deleting and distorting data, e.g. [12,13]. Despite DWG’s prompt response with bans, new accounts continued to emerge. The timing of these edits, coinciding with Israeli military’s airstrikes on Gaza in response to Hamas’s October 7 attack, along with changeset comments such as “There is no country Israel & Free Palestine,” clearly indicated a political motivation behind the vandalism. Eventually, 13 new accounts (identified here based on bans and changeset comments) responsible for 279 changesets had succeeded in deleting large portions of Tel Aviv (see Fig. 1a), distorting entities across Israel (see Fig. 1b), and even altering coastlines in Lebanon, Turkey, Cyprus, Greece, Egypt, and the Gaza Strip itself, likely due to the automated edits not excluding entities extending beyond Israel, such as the Levantine Sea [14] (see Fig. 1c). One unique case of counter-vandalism was registered when part of the Gaza strip was annexed into Israel “[i]n response to the deletion of Tel Aviv” [15].

Figure 1. Screenshots of the OSM website, 25 October 2024. (a) Data deletion in Tel Aviv’s center; (b) Northern Tel Aviv - diagonal streets are the result of distortions, the orange line is Israel’s border which was also distorted; (c) Beirut, Lebanon, near the US embassy - the coastline (in orange) crosses to land at one point, the international border is also distorted. Source: ©OpenStreetMap contributors.

A secondary chain of events unfolded in response to these attacks, characterized by collaboration between the Israeli mapping community and the DWG. Despite historical tensions between the Israeli community and the DWG [3], a close partnership emerged. On October 22, 2024, a DWG member initiated a dedicated thread on the Israel OSM Community Forum [16] and was subsequently invited to join the OSM_Israel Telegram group, establishing two direct communication channels for reporting new vandal accounts and coordinating data reverts. A clear division of labor emerged: users reported issues, the DWG issued bans and implemented reverts (one highly active Israeli user was unique in also engaging with the reverting processes). The collaboration however extended beyond immediate damage control. Responding to local mappers’ comments in both channels, the DWG member referenced a GitHub issue regarding the possibility of limiting edit volumes [17], explicitly encouraging community members to contribute their thoughts. Although the idea of a rate limiting was not new – the issue had been open since August 2019 – it gained traction after two Israeli community members joined the discussion on October 23, 2023, posting comments which directly addressed the situation in Israel, with one referencing the

comment from the Israel OSM Community Forum in which the DWG member mentioned the issue. This sparked widespread discussion, leading to a new pull request issued by an OSM system administrator on October 29, which he merged into the master branch on November 15, 2023 [18]. Today, the daily rate limit is enforced and has been expanded to include a geographical limit on changeset size [19].

The dynamics behind this significant shift in OSM's strategy – from reactive damage control to proactive vulnerability reduction – offer valuable insights into the governance systems and power dynamics that shape the project's vulnerability and resilience. In the context of data contributions, OSM operates as a 'do-ocracy,' where power is derived from action [20]. Typically, this system is beneficial, as those who contribute more hold greater influence. However, it also introduces a significant vulnerability: the case here shows that within this governance system, any individual user has the power to undermine OSM. The rate limit, designed to reduce this vulnerability by curbing individual power, challenges the do-ocratic model (concerns regarding its impact on active users were indeed voiced in [17] and [18]). Furthermore, the measure's implementation relied on a mechanism foreign to do-ocracy, i.e. mobilizing contributors to support the initiative. This process was necessary because, in terms of management, crowdsourced geodata projects like OSM are governed by a different system comprising three interacting components [21]: the project, where goals and procedures are established, the data-contributing users, and the technical infrastructure. In this model, power is primarily based on position and concentrated within the project sphere, particularly in roles like the OSM system administrator. However, transitions between these spheres are possible, as demonstrated by the ad-hoc coalition formed between the DWG member and community members. Despite the general division of labor, local mappers' involvement in vandalism detection and data reverts blurred the boundaries between the spheres. This interaction supported the DWG member's invitation to local mappers to engage more actively by endorsing the rate limit concept. The two governance systems thus intersected, with a do-ocratic approach used to penetrate the hierarchical structure and effect significant change. However, the outcome further differentiates contributors from the project, shifting more power towards the project and away from individual contributors, thus widening the gap between these two spheres. Indeed, concerns have already been raised regarding the rate limit's impacts [22].

In conclusion, the interplay between these two governance systems in OSM is dynamic, converging when actions facilitate boundary crossings and diverging when the project asserts power over contributors. This tension between reducing vulnerability and enhancing openness is central to the project's evolution: hierarchy reduces vulnerability through greater control, which also creates participation barriers, while a do-ocratic approach fosters both openness and vulnerability. Yet, this interplay is also a source of resilience; the flexibility of boundaries inherent in do-ocracy can expedite adaptation processes, as seen in the temporary coalition's mobilization. However, such efforts must be approached cautiously, as shifts in the balance between the two systems can have profound implications, such as using a do-ocratic approach to limit openness. Additionally, it is noteworthy that other significant vandalism cases, such as those related to the Russia-Ukraine conflict [4], did not lead to substantial changes within OSM. Whether this was due to an inability to mobilize local contributors or other factors remains unclear. Therefore, further research is needed to determine whether the factors outlined here are essential for mitigating vulnerability or represent just one pathway to such outcomes.

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